

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Kadirova Marg'uba Buriyevna

MEANING-BASED APPROACH AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO FORM-BASED APPROACH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

2023/MAY

